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TOOLBOX FOR INTERNATIONALISATION: A DIGITAL BOX FULL OF RELEVANT INSIGHTS, HANDS-ON SOLUTIONS AND USEFUL TIPS

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This workshop introduces a toolbox for internationalisation of education, aimed at university lecturers in for example an international classroom teaching situation. This topic is important because more and more programmes are taught in English with a mix of students with a diverse background. This diversity in the international classroom includes national and ethnic backgrounds, gender, age, study discipline, beliefs and religions, spiritual and sexual orientations, life experiences, (dis)ability, etc. To maximise the benefits of this mix and to offer each student the same opportunity for study success is not an easy task. The purpose of the workshop is to discuss issues in the international classroom, share experiences and give each other tips using the toolbox for internationalisation.

The toolbox is designed for lecturers to support them in their development towards a true international classroom. The toolbox is structured around definitions of the internationalisation issues addressed, practical solutions for the lecturers and references for further reading including background literature. The following topics are dealt with: the importance of internationalisation, course development, teacher competences, student preparation, and diversity in the international classroom.

Staff and lecturers from three technical universities in the Netherlands (the University of Twente, Eindhoven University of Technology and Wageningen University & Research) developed the toolbox, funded by the Centre of Engineering Education (CEE) from the Dutch technical universities organisation. The toolbox development was started after an inventory was made amongst programme directors at these institutes to find out what kind of support they need for the development and implementation of the international classroom concept and an international curriculum. The results showed that they wanted to receive training and have an online toolbox with practical tips and a useful literature.

The workshop offers the opportunity to explore the toolbox and to discuss with colleagues various issues/ cases concerning the international classroom. After a short plenary introduction, we will split up in sub-groups, where we will discuss a selected case from the international classroom and explore it from several perspectives, using the CEE Toolbox for Internationalisation. Several cases will be available, from which participants can choose the case of their interest. The practice-based cases address issues like assessment, group work, and student integration. It is also possible to bring in your own situation.

Programme:

0-15 mn Plenary introduction with awareness exercise

15-45 mn Subgroups – Zoom break-out rooms (choose one)

A. How can we internationalise our programmes?

Research shows that to prepare students for global citizenship and the global workforce, cross-cultural interactions are beneficial to students. In order for students to learn from cross-cultural interactions these interactions have to be organised, because learning is not a natural consequence of having students from diverse backgrounds in the classroom.

In this subgroup, you will explore how you can organise learning from cross-cultural interactions in your programmes and curriculum, using the Toolbox.

B. Teaching competences for teaching in an international classroom

Intercultural competence is not automatically developed just by teaching in an international environment. Intercultural competence should be seen as a process, that involves awareness, self-reflection, reflexivity and the development of knowledge and comprehension about cultural differences.

In this subgroup, you will explore the competences that are needed for teaching in an international context, as well as the process to acquire these competences, making use of the resources in the Toolbox.

C. Preparing students for learning in an international classroom

Preparing students for learning in an international classroom involves different aspects, from setting the general context of cultural awareness, developing intercultural competences, to raising interaction between students.

In this subgroup, you will explore the different aspects of preparing students for learning in an international classroom, making use of the Toolbox.

D. Diversity: going beyond cultural differences

Diversity in the classroom goes beyond what is visible like gender, age, ethnic background, dress-code, etc. It also includes various cultural differences, interdisciplinarity, diverse socio-economic backgrounds, sex-orientation (for ex. LGBT), physical disabilities, learning styles, specific talents, etc.

In this subgroup, you will explore how to develop awareness and respect for diversity and how to move towards inclusion in your classroom, using the Toolbox.

45-60 mn Harvest of the subgroups and wrap-up

The target group for the workshop are university lecturers and staff involved in designing and teaching international classrooms.